

Search for Physiologically Active Compounds. Part-XXII. Synthesis of 4-(2-Furyl) and 4-(2-Furyl)-3-Phenyl Coumarins

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Some 4-(2-furyl) and 4-(2-furyl)-3-phenyl coumarins have been prepared for the first time from the respective 2-hydroxyphenyl furyl ketones adopting Perkin and Bargellini procedures. In general, 4-(2-furyl)-3-phenyl coumarins are more toxic to fish than 4-(2-furyl) coumarins. Of all the compounds tested, 7-methoxy-4-(2-furyl)-3-phenyl coumarin exhibited the maximum activity towards fish. Introduction of 3-phenyl substituent in 4-(2-furyl) coumarins does not bring about any significant change in the bacteriostatic activity. The uv., i.r. and n.m.r. spectral data of some of the compounds are presented.

IN a general scheme to investigate the effect of a heterocyclic substituent in the pyrone ring on the physiological activity of coumarins, the synthesis of 3-(2-furyl) coumarins¹ was reported earlier from this laboratory. The present paper deals with the synthesis, spectral data, fish toxicity and bacteriostatic activity of 4-(2-furyl) and 4-(2-furyl)-3-phenyl coumarins. The only reference available in literature on these compounds is that of Khaiken and coworkers² who reported the synthesis of 7,8-dihydroxy 4-(2-furyl) coumarin by Pechmann condensation of ethyl furoyl acetate with pyrogallol using 85% sulphuric acid as the condensing agent.

For the synthesis of 4-(2-furyl) coumarins the methods available for the preparation of 4-phenyl coumarins³⁻⁹ can be adopted. Of these Perkin

reaction has been made use of in the present investigation. The intermediate, 2-hydroxyphenyl furyl ketones required have been prepared by either Fries migration or Friedel-Crafts acylation procedures. By the Fries migration of furoyl esters of the corresponding phenols, 5-methyl¹⁰, 5-chloro¹¹, 5-bromo¹¹, 3,5-dichloro¹¹ and 1-hydroxy-2-naphthyl furyl ketones¹⁰ have been prepared. In addition, 5-chloro-4-methyl-2-hydroxyphenyl furyl ketone has been prepared for the first time adopting the above procedure. The 4-methoxy-2-hydroxyphenyl furyl ketone has now been prepared in improved yields by Friedel-Crafts reaction of 2-furoyl chloride on resorcinol dimethyl ether. The properties of the compound are in complete agreement with the one prepared by Borsche¹² adopting Hoesch reaction of

Fig. 1

TABLE I—4-(2-FURYL) COUMARINS

Sl.No.	4-(2-furyl)coumarin ^a	m.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	Mol. Formula	Analysis (%)			
					Found		Required	
				C	H	C	H	
1.	6-Methyl	171	59	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₃	74.54	4.48	74.32	4.43
2.	6-Chloro	178	72	C ₁₃ H ₇ ClO ₃	63.74	2.84	63.42	2.85
3.	6-Bromo	174	52	C ₁₃ H ₇ BrO ₃	53.91	2.56	53.64	2.42
4.	7-Methoxy	150	60	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₄	69.14	4.23	69.42	4.03
5.	6,8-Dichloro	160	52	C ₁₃ H ₆ Cl ₂ O ₃	55.42	2.31	55.55	2.13
6.	7-Methyl-6-chloro	200	67	C ₁₄ H ₈ ClO ₃	64.57	3.89	64.48	3.72
7.	7,8-Benzo	239	55	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ O ₃	78.01	3.98	77.85	3.82
8.	6-Methyl-3-phenyl	114	54	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ O ₃	79.01	4.70	79.47	4.63
9.	6-Chloro-3-phenyl	139	60	C ₁₉ H ₁₁ ClO ₃	70.41	3.90	70.79	3.84
10.	6-Bromo-3-phenyl	150	50	C ₁₉ H ₁₁ BrO ₃	64.22	3.08	64.46	3.08
11.	7-Methoxy-3-phenyl	147	53	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ O ₄	75.81	4.52	75.48	4.41
12.	6,8-Dichloro-3-phenyl	197	49	C ₁₉ H ₁₀ Cl ₂ O ₃	64.37	2.90	64.04	2.81
13.	7-Methyl-6-chloro-3-phenyl	206	65	C ₂₀ H ₁₃ ClO ₃	71.19	3.91	71.44	3.87
14.	7,8-Benzo-3-phenyl	211	48	C ₂₃ H ₁₄ O ₃	81.51	4.13	81.66	4.23

^a = Recrystallised from alcohol.

pyromuconitrile (2-cyanofuran) with resorcinol and subsequent methylation of 4-hydroxyl group.

The 2-hydroxyphenyl furyl ketones (I) thus prepared have been condensed with fused sodium acetate and acetic anhydride under Perkin reaction conditions to give rise to the corresponding 4-(2-furyl) coumarins (II). The 4-(2-furyl)-3-phenyl coumarins (III) have been prepared by allowing 2-hydroxyphenyl furyl ketones to react with sodium phenyl acetate and acetic anhydride by adopting the procedure of Bargellini¹³ modified by Seshadri¹⁴.

The compounds prepared have been listed in Table 1 along with their analytical data.

The ultraviolet spectra of 6- and 7-substituted 4-(2-furyl) coumarins are similar to the corresponding 4-unsubstituted coumarins¹⁵⁻¹⁷ (Table 2). The furyl substituent in 4-position has no significant influence on the higher wave length band. While 6-methyl coumarin was noticed to absorb at λ_{max} 320 nm¹⁵, 6-methyl-4-(2-furyl) coumarin has shown absorption at λ_{max} 325 nm. Substitution of a phenyl group at 3-position of 4-(2-furyl) coumarins produces a bathochromic shift of the longer wave length band by about 10-14 nm probably due to increase in steric strain.

TABLE 2—U.V. AND I.R. DATA OF 4-(2-FURYL) COUMARINS

Sl. No.	4-(2-furyl)coumarin	U.V. λ_{max} in nm (log ϵ)	I.R.	
			>C=O cm ⁻¹	
1.	6-Methyl	253(4.33), 285(4.17), 325(4.10)	1740	
2.	6-Chloro	250(4.22), 281(4.21), 329(4.27)	1740	
3.	7-Methoxy	241(4.14), 337(4.32)	1735	
4.	6,8-Dichloro	238(4.22), 331(4.24)	1735	
5.	7-Methyl-6-chloro	222(4.37), 330(4.24)	1740	
6.	6-Methyl-3-phenyl	256(4.43), 286(4.02), 338(4.07)	1735	
7.	6-Chloro-3-phenyl	250(4.07), 281(4.25), 339(4.26)	1740	
8.	7-Methoxy-3-phenyl	241(4.29), 347(4.22)	1740	
9.	6,8-Dichloro-3-phenyl	228(4.21), 280(4.24), 345(4.01)	1735	
10.	7-Methyl-6-chloro	225(4.43), 278(4.10), 340(4.14)	1740	

In the Infra red region, the coumarins showed a typical carbonyl absorption around 1740 cm⁻¹ (Table 2). Most of the peaks that were assigned for the 2-substituted furans¹⁸ in the region 1600-800 cm⁻¹ are also present in these 4-(2-furyl) coumarins.

The N.M.R. Spectra of 7-methoxy-4-(2-furyl) and 7-methoxy-4-(2-furyl)-3-phenyl coumarins have been taken and the data are presented in Table 3. The

TABLE 3—N.M.R. SPECTRA OF 7-METHOXY-4-(2-FURYL) COUMARIN (IV) AND 7-METHOXY-4-(2-FURYL)-3-PHENYL COUMARINS (V).

Compound	Assignment	Value (δ)	Multiplicity
7-Methoxy-4-(2-furyl) coumarin.	Methoxyl (a)	3.87	Singlet
	Coumarin 3H (b)	6.42	Singlet
	Furyl 4H (c)	6.58	Quartet.
	Coumarin 8H (d)	6.77	Singlet
	Furyl 3H (e)	6.85	Quartet.
	Coumarin 6H (f)	6.92	Doublet
	Furyl 5H (g)	7.70	Quartet.
	Coumarin 5H (h)	8.00	Doublet
7-Methoxy-4-(2-furyl)-3-Phenyl coumarin	Methoxyl (a)	3.91	Singlet
	Furyl 4H (b)	6.42	Quartet.
	Furyl 3H (c)	6.75	Quartet.
	Coumarin 8H (d)	6.91	Singlet
	Phenyl protons (e)	7.20	Singlet
	Coumarin 6H (f)		
	Furyl 5H (g)	7.50	Quartet.
	Coumarin 5H (h)	7.66	Doublet

signals that were assigned for 3-substituted coumarins¹⁹ and 2-substituted furans²⁰ are present in these two 4-(2-furyl) coumarins. The (δ) values of 3,4, and 5-protons of furyl moiety in 7-methoxy-4-(2-furyl) coumarin are higher by around 0.1-0.2 δ when compared to 4-(2-furyl)-3-phenyl coumarins. This probably may be due to the shielding effect of phenyl moiety at 3-position on the adjacent furyl moiety *i.e.*, at 4-position on the coumarin molecule.

Fig. 2

From the results of testing, it is observed that a 2-furyl substituent at 4-position of coumarins significantly contributed to the activity against fish (Table 4). The introduction of a 3-phenyl substituent in 4-(2-furyl) coumarin series results in enhancing the toxicity. Thus a 2-furyl substituent at 4-position is similar to a methyl group which is known to enhance the toxicity of the corresponding 3-phenyl coumarins²¹. Among the fourteen coumarins tested, 7-methoxy-4-(2-furyl)-3-phenyl coumarin exhibited the highest toxicity.

Among the fourteen 4-(2-furyl) coumarins tested for their bacteriostatic activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus coli* and *Bacillus subtilis* (Table 4), 6-chloro and 6-bromo coumarins are active against all the bacteria at 100 ppm.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in a sulphuric acid bath and are uncorrected. I.R. Spectra were taken on Perkin Elmer-I Model 137 using nujol mull and U.V. Spectra were recorded on a Beckmann D.B. spectrophotometer using methanol as solvent. N.M.R. has been taken on a Varian 60 MHz using tetramethyl silane as internal reference and deuterated chloroform as solvent.

General procedure for the synthesis of 4-(2-furyl) coumarins :

o-Hydroxyphenyl furyl ketone (0.015 mole), fused sodium acetate (0.10 mole) and acetic anhydride (0.50 mole) were refluxed together at 170°-80° for 24 hrs in an oil bath. The dark mixture was then poured on crushed ice while stirring and left overnight. Water was decanted off and semi solid was treated with small quantity of cold alcohol. The solid that was separated was filtered and recrystallised from alcohol.

General procedure for the synthesis of 4-(2-furyl)-3-phenyl coumarins :

o-Hydroxyphenyl furyl ketone (0.015 mole), fused sodium phenyl acetate (0.20 mole) and acetic anhydride (0.50 mole) were refluxed at 170°-80° for 8 hrs in an oil bath. The reaction mixture was poured on crushed ice with stirring and kept aside overnight. The pasty mass thus settled was triturated with cold alcohol and the solid that separated was recrystallised from alcohol.

7-Methyl-6-chloro-4-(2-furyl) coumarin :

a) *3-Methyl-4-chloro furoyl benzoate* : A mixture of 3-chloro-2-methyl phenol (14.3 g), anhydrous benzene (25 ml.), magnesium (1.2 g.) and furoyl chloride¹⁰

TABLE 4—FISH TOXICITY AND BACTERIOSTATIC ACTIVITY DATA OF 4-(2-FURYL) COUMARINS

Sl.No.	4-(2-furyl)coumarin	Fish toxicity 20 P.P.M. Turning-time in minutes	Bacteriostatic activity					
			S.A.		B.S.		B.C.	
			A	B	A	B	A	B
1.	6-Methyl	20.5	±	+	±	+	✓	+
2.	6-Chloro	24.5	±	+	±	+	-	+
3.	6-Bromo	27.0	±	+	-	+	+	+
4.	7-Methoxy	3.0	±	+	+		±	+
5.	6,8-Dichloro	69.0	+		+		±	+
6.	7-Methyl-6-Chloro	29.0	±	+	±	+	±	+
7.	7,8-Benzo	Not active in 24 hours	+		+		+	+
8.	6-Methyl-3-phenyl	12.5	±	+	±	+	±	+
9.	6-Chloro-3-phenyl	11.5	±	+	±	+	±	+
10.	6-Bromo-3-phenyl	10.2	±	+	±	+	-	+
11.	7-Methoxy-3-phenyl	2.0	±	+	+		+	+
12.	7-Methyl-6-chloro-3-phenyl	25.1	±	+	±	+	±	+
13.	6,8-Dichloro-3-phenyl	51.0	±	+	±	+	+	+
14.	7.8-Benzo-3-phenyl	Not active in 24 hours	+		+		+	+

S.A. = *Staphylococcus aureus*
 B.S. = *Bacillus subtilis*
 B.C. = *Bacillus coli*

+ = Full growth
 - = No growth
 ± = Partial growth.

A = 100 ppm.
 B = 10 ppm.

(14 g.) was refluxed on a water-bath for 1 hr. Magnesium was filtered off, the benzene was removed under reduced pressure and the residue was taken in ether and it was washed with 1% sodium hydroxide solution, then with water. The ethereal layer was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Ether was distilled off and the residue was recrystallised from aqueous ethanol in colourless flakes (18.9 g.; 80%), m.p. 110° (Found: C, 60.61; H, 3.82; $C_{12}H_9ClO_3$ requires C, 60.90; H, 3.80%).

b) 5-Chloro-4-methyl-2-hydroxyphenyl furyl ketone : The above ester (a) (17 g.) was dissolved in carbon disulphide (180 ml.) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (18 g.) was added slowly while cooling and stirring and heated on a water-bath for 2 hrs. Solvent was removed and the residue was heated for 2 hrs in an oil-bath. It was cooled and decomposed by adding dilute hydrochloric acid. The solid thus separated was recrystallised from aqueous methanol into lemon yellow needles (10 g., 59%), m.p. 96° (Found: C, 60.61; H, 3.74; $C_{12}H_9ClO_3$ requires C, 60.90; H, 3.80%).

4-Methoxy-2-hydroxyphenyl furyl ketone :

To a solution of 1,3-dimethoxybenzene²² (13.8 g.), furoyl chloride (14 g.) and 1,2-dichloroethane (50 ml.), anhydrous aluminium chloride (27 g.) was added in small portions while cooling and shaking. The mixture was then heated on a water-bath for 2 hrs, poured on crushed ice containing hydrochloric acid and kept aside for 2 hrs. The yellow semi-solid that separated was taken in ether, washed well with water and extracted with 5% sodium hydroxide solution. The alkali solution was acidified under cooling. The yellow solid thus separated was filtered and dried. It was passed through silica gel column using benzene as the eluting solvent. 4-Methoxy-2-hydroxyphenyl furyl ketone passed down in the first fraction which on concentration and cooling separated into shiny lemon yellow needles (12 g; 62%), m.p. 94° (Found: C, 64.30; H, 4.60; $C_{12}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 64.17; H, 4.58%). Lit. m.p.¹² 92°.

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